

Article

Impact of Climate Change on Academic Achievement of Learners with Disabilities in College of Education Akwanga, Nasarawa State

Abdulkadir Egya Odula, Timothy Dave Tashi, Nendi Goyit John & Nekre Zamwa Chube

Editor-in-chief
Dr. Jummai Jerry

Editors

1. Prof. Abu Egwa Ozegya
2. Prof. Gladys Belinda Babudoh
3. Prof. Terfa Ahon Adaka
4. Dr. Rufus Olanrewaju Adebisi

Nasarawa State University Journal of Special and Inclusive Education (NSUJSIE)

ISSN: 3121-729X

Article

Impact of Climate Change on Academic Achievement of Learners with Disabilities in College of Education Akwanga, Nasarawa State

Abdulkadir Egya Odula ^{1*}, Timothy Dave Tashi ², Nendi Goyit John ³ & Nekre Zamwa Chube ²

¹ Department of Curriculum Studies
College of Education Akwanga,
Nasarawa State

² Department of Special Education
College of Education Akwanga,
Nasarawa State

³ Ministry of Education,
Jos, Plateau State

*Correspondence: timdave1985@gmail.com (TDT)

check for
updates

Citation: Odula, A. E., Tashi, T. D., John, N. G. & Chube, N. Z. (2026). Impact of Climate Change on Academic Achievement of Learners with Disabilities in College of Education Akwanga, Nasarawa State. *Nas. State Uni. J. of Spe. & Inclusive Edu*; 1(1), 178-184. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19473347>

Academic Editor: Dr. Jummai Jerry

Received: 14 November, 2025

Revised: 8 December, 2025

Accepted: 3 February, 2026

Published: 1 April, 2026

Abstract: *The challenges and threats that climate change has caused in present dispensation cannot be over emphasized. This paper aims at examining the impacts of climate change on academic achievement of learners with disabilities” highlights the definition of climate change as long-term warming of the planet due to increase in the average global temperature, caused mainly by human activities such as burning fossil fuels, deforestation and other daily practices which releases greenhouse gasses into the atmosphere that results to change in weather patterns, rising sea levels and other environmental impacts. The paper also focused on educational implications of climate change on academic achievement of learners with disabilities. Lastly, conclusion and recommendations were drawn as: There is need for curriculum planners to develop climate responsive education plans as this will prioritize accessibility and support for learners with disabilities and training should as well be given to those who are saddled with curriculum implementation.*

Copyright: © 2026 by the authors. Published by Department of Special Education, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, in collaboration with Zhimmai Publishing House, Keffi, Nigeria. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Keywords: Climate change, Academic Achievement, learning disabilities, Nasarawa State

Introduction

One of the most challenging and trending issues learners with disabilities faces in the 21st century, this poses danger to their health, education, food security and economic stability. It is considered as one of the topical issues across the globe and also one of the most escalating and pressing global challenge in the present dispensation. As climate crises increases globally, so it impacts negatively on the vulnerable individuals among those are learners with disabilities, individuals who are uniquely challenged and other additional challenges as a result of the environment compounding to the already existing problems. As temperature rises globally, the weather increases as well leaving the burden on learners with disabilities. Lancet countdown report on health and climate change, produced in collaboration with World Health Organization opine that in that heat-related mortality have increased by 23% since 1990 with an average of 546,000 heat-related deaths annually, while the average person experienced 16 days of dangerous heat in 2004 that would have occurred without climate change. (WHO, 2025).

While climate change impacts negatively on all learners, those with disabilities suffer more in their physical, intellectual, developmental, as well as sensory impairment. To mitigate the various dangers climate has caused to humanity especially in the education of learners with disabilities, all hands must be on deck. Various stakeholders both in communities as well as schools and research affiliate must be engaged.

It is imperative to clearly define the term climate change for the sake of clarity. The term climate change in a more simplified way refers to rise in the earth's temperature as a result of human activities such as pollution, causing big changes in weather patterns and environment. UNECEF sees climate change as devastating threatening component of society. Research found out that half of the world children, almost around 1 billion living in countries at a high risk of climate change as it impacts them negatively causing more harm to the already existing challenge. Climate change is a key factor that leads to poverty and hunger and school inaccessibility as well as teaching and learning of learners with disabilities. Academic Achievement according to Spinath (2012) is conceptualized as the performance outcomes that indicate the extent to which a person has accomplished specific goals that were the focus of activities in instructional environments, specifically school, college, and the university. This help in showing evidences of academic attainment of a learner and to also indicate areas where the learner needs to be helped so as to achieve their goals. Learners with disabilities on the other hand according to Mada Accessibility Glossary (2020) refers to the group of learners with learning, physical, developmental, behavioral, emotional and communication difficulties who would benefit from additional support within the education environment, often catered through ICT and assistive Technologies.

Negative impact of climate change on education of learners with Disabilities

Climate change is one of the factors that is militating against the educational achievement of learners with disabilities in modern era as it impedes learning. Factors such as rise in temperature, flood among many are common factors. Temperature rise makes learning environment to be unconducive and inhabitable learning for teaching learning thereby affecting learners from attaining their educational milestone. Extreme temperature can exacerbate health conditions of learners this may lead to increased absence in school as it may affect the academic achievement of learners. In situations where they are at school, they may not be able to concentrate.

Damage and inaccessibility of school structures

Flood, hurricanes, wildfire and extreme weather condition damage school buildings, road hinders learners with mobility limitation from gaining access to school environment. Learners with mobility defect find it difficult to access school to learn. Such damages are insurmountable to school attendance. This may further limit the chances of attaining any meaningful development academically. There are also situations where flood may cause displacement, trauma as well as stress which may affect the attention of learners and as well cause health related matters increasing the rate of absenteeism. The 2025 thematic review published in Discover Education, which analyzed 71 peer-reviewed studies identified accessibility challenge as one of the critical barriers faced by learners with disabilities during climate related disaster.

International organization of migration (2009) reports that, the global temperature will rise

between 2 to 5 degrees centigrade at the end of this century which cause of less habitable

chances for people on earth due to climate change, destruction of agricultural land and water

crisis, the result also predicts that in the next 40 years 25 million to 1 billion could be displaced as a result of climate change (Laczko & Aghazarm 2009). Climate change is the most devastating challenge that pauses danger to humanity in modern era, as it affects human social life and cultural identity is at risk.

Rise in sea level

Factors such as rising in sea level due to melting of glaciers which erase the lands, houses including schools where learners with disabilities learn, that result to destruction and disappearance of people cultural heritage. The learners with disabilities who happen to be from the endangered area are forcefully displaced which cause of identity loss and cultural insecurity (Krupocin & Jesse 2020). This grossly affects their education. The composition of earth atmosphere and structure of surface have dramatically change due to human activities which directly affect the earth' balance regarding energy that cause climate change. Such activities change in rainfall pattern, rising sea level that cause flooding, increase drought frequency in land that also increase earth' temperature (Fakana, 2020).As the climate events are increasing day by day and affecting our environment but the relationship between climate change and academic performance is closely related to each other and becoming the emerging concern worldwide, number of students all around the world are facing limitations to reach out academic resources and effective participation.

Extreme Weather Condition

The extreme weather condition due to climate change disrupts educational functional activities, which cause of school closure, precipitating learning loss, and infrastructure vulnerability. In other words, climate change pauses health challenges to learners with disabilities thereby adding other challenges to the existing condition which is disabilities. This results School closure due to extreme weather condition. It is estimated at about 75 percent in the past 20 years and it affects more than 5 million people (Marin at al. 2024). Research reveals that about 75 million children's educational activities have been disrupted due to natural disaster that is projected by severity of climate change (Agnafors & Sydsjo, 2021). Climate change is the most serious issue of twenty first century having a profound psychological impact resulting in harming the cognition process and academic achievement of learners. The extreme weather events are triggering to mental health issues (anxiety, depression, panic, phobias)

(Burke, Williams, Chandler, Haywood, Lunt, & Otto-Bliesner, 2018).

Obekpa & Usman (2024) conducted research on “The impact of climate change on student’s academic performance on Kogi, Nigeria. This impact indirectly poses pressure on families economically and results in drop out rate, increase number in child labor and early marriage among young girls (Venegas, Schwarz, & Sabarwal 2024). These impact cause of less school attendance and poor performance in academic activities (Francis, 2014). Impact of environmental disruption includes physical illness and trauma from natural disaster and creating educational disruption (Kearney, Ellis, & Arcaina 2024). Research study investigates the influence of climate change awareness and educational authority on the academic achievement of students. On the basis of their study, they found that integration of climate change education, parental involvement, using innovative technology and fostering environmental stewardship can improve student academic outcomes. According to the participants the addition of climate change topics (renewable energy, waste and energy conservation) and taking practical initiatives like tree plantation can improve student performance and engagement. Climatic factors are hindering children to make decision to learn and acquire certain skills for an effective participation. Rise in temperature, resulting in hot classrooms even teachers are unable to spend considerable time in classrooms. Excessive flood occurrence limits student’s access to learning institutions and resulting in dropout (Ofem et al. 2024) In situations where this keep reoccurring years after years may result to dropping from school to be safe. Climate change is one of the serious global issues that requires urgent attention and sustainable actions to protect the environment. (Nanthakumar, Sathikumarn & Sivashankar, 2018). There is need for synergy between Schools and communities to work together to ensure safety, health and supportive learning environment to secure student education and future. (Hussaini, 2023). Abrupt rainfalls cause landslides road blockage and flood, while rise in temperature causes melting of glaciers resulting rising in sea level. These factors resulting in various adverse events cause damage to different sectors.

Educational implications of climate change to learners with Disabilities

Climate change has caused a lot damages to Learners with disabilities serving as a stronghold that is limiting their meaningful educational achievement. This has led to migration in search for habitable and safe havens. Learners displaced from their communities in some cases, this forces them to be absent from school. Adequate measures must be put in place to combat this menace so as to give them sense of belonging as they are part and parcel of the society.

- **Health issues**

It is worthy of mention that climate disasters have detrimental effect on the health of children with disabilities, as they often lose access to crucial medical treatments and other essential healthcare services. New diseases are spreading to areas where they never existed before. Education is repeatedly disrupted by disasters, and negative coping mechanisms like child labor and child marriage are on the increase. Climate change can significantly impact the academic achievement of learners with disabilities disrupting learning environments through climate-related events like floods, heat waves, or storms, all these can damage schools, cause closures and disrupting learning.

- **Trauma and Anxiety**

Again, climate disasters cause trauma to learners with disabilities through events that happened and all the climate disaster experienced such as death of loved ones and lot more. This is not just about the physical impacts created, extreme weather events, it causes uncertainty and unpredictable mindset

and fear of what will happen in the future, worries and stress

- **Social Isolation and Exclusion**

Climate change affects the social life and well-being of learners with disabilities. This leads to increased social isolation and exclusion, particularly the vulnerable population where learners with disabilities constitute part. Rise in temperature and environmental degradation have a way of disrupting social connections and livelihood of people. This happens through displacement and migration. This can lead to loss of cultural identity and social networking.

CONCLUSION

To conclude this, it is worthy of mention that climate change poses significant threats to the educational rights, opportunities and academic achievement of learners with disabilities, exacerbating existing inequalities and creating new barriers to education. To mitigate these impacts, inclusive and resilient education systems are crucial. There is need to be intentional on making policy frameworks and laws where no learner is left out regardless of disability or climate vulnerability. Programs such as caring for our world should be initiated and demonstrated with appropriate adaptation and support to learners with disabilities.

However, the challenge of climate change requires immediate and sustained actions from various authorities. Urgent effort must be made through teachers, stakeholders, policy makers and implementer to ensure this menace is reduced to the beeriest minimum.

SUGGESTIONS

The following recommendations have been made:

1. **Inclusive Education Planning:** There is need for curriculum planners to develop climate responsive education plans as this will prioritize accessibility and support for learners with disabilities.
2. **Teacher trainings:** People saddled with the responsibilities of planning curriculum should take it as a matter of concern to include in the curriculum teacher training or workshops in the aspect of climate change which have negative effects on learners with disabilities and as well put in monitoring mechanisms. This will go a long way to help them.
3. **Teacher Training:** Provide teachers with training on supporting learners with disabilities in climate-affected contexts.
4. **Community Engagement:** Host communities and families where people with disabilities stays should be sensitized on various life-threatening effects of climate change as it affects individuals with disabilities.

REFERENCES

- Agnafors, S., Barmark, M., & Sydsjö, G. (2021). Mental health and academic performance: A study on selection and causation effects from childhood to early adulthood. *Social psychiatry and psychiatric epidemiology*, 56(5), 857-866.
- Ahmed, S., Naudhani, T., Khan, S. S., & Wazir, S. (2025). Bridging a gap: Assessing climate change impacts on girls' education and developing a resilient learning system. *Contemporary Journal of Social Science Review*, 3(1), 1455-1464.
- Anderson, A. A. (2017). Effects of social media use on climate change opinion, knowledge, and behavior. In *Oxford research encyclopedia of climate science*.
- Brikel, H. (2024). Climate change and Students performance. *Psychology and Education*, 61(11), 1553-6939.
- Burke, K. D., Williams, J. W., Chandler, M. A., Haywood, A. M., Lunt, D. J., & Otto-Bliesner, B. L. (2018). Pliocene and Eocene provide best analogs for near-future climates. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(52), 13288-13293.
- Eckstein, E., Pyrski, M., Pinto, S., Freichel, M., Vennekens, R., & Zufall, F. (2020). Cyclic regulation of Trpm4 expression in female vomeronasal neurons driven by ovarian sex hormones. *Molecular and Cellular Neuroscience*, 105, 103495.
- Fakana, S. T. (2020). Causes of climate change. *Global Journal of Science Frontier Research*, 20, 7-12.
- García-Marín, L. M., Campos, A. I., Diaz-Torres, S., Rabinowitz, J. A., Ceja, Z., Mitchell, B. L., ... & Shin, J. (2024). Genomic analysis of intracranial and subcortical brain volumes yields polygenic scores accounting for variation across ancestries. *Nature genetics*, 56(11), 2333-2344.
- Gust, S. (2024). (Not) going to school in times of climate change: Natural disasters and student achievement (No. 413).
- Hegney, D. G., Craigie, M., Hemsworth, D., Osseiran-Moisson, R., Aoun, S., Francis, K., & Drury, V. (2014). Compassion satisfaction, compassion fatigue, anxiety, depression and stress in registered nurses in Australia: study 1 results. *Journal of nursing management*, 22(4), 506-518.
- Hussaini, M. H. A. L. (2023). Impact of climate on student education and their future development. *Int J Integr Sci*, 2(4), 513-22.
- Jesse, B. J., heinrichs, H. U., & kucksinrichs, W. (2019). Adapting the theory of resilience to energy systems: a review and outlook, *Energy, Sustainability and Society*, 9(1), 27.
- Kearney, C. A., Ellis, K., & Arcaina, V. J. (2024). Climate change injustice and school attendance and absenteeism: Proximal and distal ecological links. In *Frontiers in Education* (Vol. 9, p. 1455430). Frontiers Media SA.
- Krupocin, D., & Krupocin, J. (2020). The impact of climate change on cultural security. *Journal of Strategic Security*, 13(4), 1-28.

- Laczko, F., & Aghazarm, C. (2009). *Migration. Environment and Climate Change: Assessing the Evidence*, Geneva: International Organization for Migration.
- Leal Filho, W., AbeldañoZuñiga, R. A., Sierra, J., Dinis, M. A. P., Corazza, L., Nagy, G. J., & Aina, Y. A. (2024). An assessment of priorities in handling climate change impacts on infrastructures. *Scientific Reports*, 14(1), 14147.
- Nanthakumar, C., Sakthikumar, M., & Sivashankar, G. (2018). Carbon dioxide—The frontline greenhouse gas. *Carbon*, 7 (01), 4-10.
- Nerlich, B., Koteyko, N., & Brown, B. (2010). Theory and language of climate change communication. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 1(1), 97-110.
- Obaka, p. H., & usman, h. (2024). Impact of climate change on secondary school students' academic performance in Kogi state, Nigeria.
- Ochieng, J., Knerr, B., Owuor, G., & Ouma, E. (2018). Strengthening collective action to improve marketing performance: evidence from farmer groups in Central Africa. *The journal of agricultural education and extension*, 24(2), 169-189.
- Ofem, U. J., Amanso, E. O. I., Ene, E. I., Asuquo, E. N., Ekpang, P. U., Idung, J. U. & Edeh, S. O. (2024). Re-engineering inclusive classroom assessment practices in a digitalized environment. The mediating effect of digital competencies, instructional practices and assessment literacy. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 10, 101150.
- Oyebola, K., Ligali, F., Owoloye, A., Erinwusi, B., Alo, Y., Musa, A. Z., & Salako, B. (2024). Machine learning—based hyperglycemia prediction: enhancing risk assessment in a cohort of undiagnosed individuals. *JMIRx Med*, 5(1), e56993.
- Sheffield, P. E., Uijtewaal, S. A., Stewart, J., & Galvez, M. P. (2017). Climate change and schools: Environmental hazards and resiliency. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 14(11), 1397.
- Spinath, B. (2012). Academic achievement. In *Oxford Bibliographies in Psychology*. Oxford University Press.
- Venegas Marin, S., Schwarz, L., & Sabarwal, S. (2024). Impacts of extreme weather events on education outcomes: a review of evidence. *The World Bank Research Observer*, 39(2).